

Case Study: Visual Analysis of UKRI Funding Instruments using the GTR Analyser Dashboard

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Abstract

This case study is based on the public *GTR Analyser* dashboard. The dashboard exposes the enhanced Gateway to Research (GtR) database through interactive analytical views for funding trends, organisation participation, team composition, spatial distribution, partnership dynamics, research-area diversity, and reported outputs and outcomes. The purpose of this document is to demonstrate how the dashboard can be used to compare UKRI funding instruments, with a particular focus on applicant-led and targeted/thematic funding, across councils, organisations, partners, places, research areas, and outcome types.

1 Introduction

In the UKRI-ESRC metascience project *What is Unique about Responsive Mode Funding?*, we have created a new enhanced GtR database and associated visual analytics dashboards as reusable infrastructure for metascience. The database contains UKRI-funded projects **from 2005 to mid-2025** and enriches the raw GtR ¹ [5] records with derived project-type labels, canonical organisation identities, sector and subsector classifications, grant-level views, career-stage indicators, and analytical tables for portfolio exploration. This report provides a case study showing how the GTR Analyser dashboard² can be used to investigate UKRI funding instruments across councils, organisations, partners, places, research areas, and outputs. The emphasis is on applicant-led funding because it is the largest project-type category in the enhanced database and is central to questions about the balance between bottom-up, investigator-led funding and targeted or mission-driven funding. The dashboard also allows the same analyses to be recomputed for targeted/thematic, training, fellowship, infrastructure, follow-up, institutional, uncertain, and all-project views. The case study is organised around four research questions:

RQ1. Funding scale and participation. How do funding instruments vary across councils in terms of project numbers, award values, team sizes, organisational participation, and geographic distribution?

RQ2. Collaboration patterns. How do collaboration patterns vary across funding instruments, including partner sectors, geography, and interdisciplinarity?

RQ3. Outputs and outcomes. What outputs and outcomes are associated with different funding instruments, and how do they vary by council and project type?

RQ4. Applicant-led versus other funding types. How do applicant-led projects compare with targeted/thematic and other funding types in terms of scale, team composition, partner engagement, sectoral reach, interdisciplinarity, and outputs?

¹<https://gtr.ukri.org/>

²GTR Analyser available at: https://projects.eidf.ac.uk/eidf256/gtr_analyser/.

The analysis uses the project-type taxonomy implemented in the enhanced database. Although the dashboard supports all project types, this case study focuses primarily on applicant-led funding, using targeted/thematic funding as the main comparator where relevant. Table 1 summarises the categories used in the dashboard and how they should be interpreted.

Table 1: Project-type taxonomy used in the *GTR Analyser* case study.

Project type	Interpretation in the dashboard
Applicant-led	Bottom-up or investigator-led schemes, including responsive-mode, standard-grant, open-call, curiosity-driven, and related schemes where applicants define the research question within council remit.
Thematic	Directed, managed, strategic, priority, mission-led, challenge-led, or targeted calls where proposals respond to a predefined funder theme or priority.
Training	Doctoral training, studentships, Centres for Doctoral Training, Doctoral Training Partnerships, CASE studentships, and related capacity-building schemes.
Fellowship	Individual career-support instruments, including fellowships, leadership fellowships, postdoctoral fellowships, early-career awards, and independent researcher schemes.
Infrastructure	Awards for equipment, facilities, capital infrastructure, research infrastructure, data infrastructure, high-performance computing, and related technical capacity.
Follow-up	Follow-on, next-stage, pathfinder, pump-priming, translational, or continuation awards that extend or develop previous research activity.
Institutional	Institution-level mechanisms awarded to organisations, such as impact acceleration accounts, public engagement awards, or strategic block-style mechanisms.
Uncertain	Projects where available scheme, call, or title metadata are insufficient for confident assignment to one of the other categories.

Results for the most recent years should be interpreted cautiously because outcomes are grouped by project start year and records for recently started projects may be incomplete.

2 How to Use the Dashboard for this Case Study

The *GTR Analyser* dashboard is structured around four main analysis menus: *High-Level Info*, *Partnership Dynamics*, *Organisation Dynamics*, and *Funding Outcomes*, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of *GTR Analyser*. The screenshot shows the *Funding Trends* tab under *High-Level Info*, filtered to display applicant-led projects across councils.

The left-hand filter panel of each sub-tab is central to the analysis: most views allow users to choose a project type, one or more councils, a year range, and, in some cases, an organisation identity mode. For the main applicant-led case study, users should usually set **Project Type = Applicant-Led** and **Councils = All Councils**. To compare against other funding instruments, the same view can be rerun with **Project Type = Thematic, Training, Fellowship, Infrastructure, Follow-up, Institutional, or All**. Table 2 summarises the dashboard tabs and sub-tabs used in this report.

The following sections use these dashboard views to examine applicant-led funding and compare it with thematic and other funding instruments where relevant.

Table 2: Dashboard navigation map for the *GTR Analyser* case study.

Top menu	Tab / sub-tab	Main use	What it helps users analyse	RQs
High-Level Info	Participation Explorer	Organisation participation	Top organisations, long-tail participation, raw versus canonical organisation identities, and concentration of projects across organisations.	Q1, Q4
High-Level Info	Funding Trends	Funding scale over time	Project counts, total funding, average project value, year-by-year trends, and council comparisons by project type.	Q1, Q4
High-Level Info	Team Composition	Team size and roles	Team-size distributions, investigator-role summaries, and differences in team composition across councils and funding instruments.	Q1, Q4
High-Level Info	Spatial Explorer	Geographic distribution	Lead-organisation locations, top places, geographic concentration, and maps by council and project type.	Q1, Q4
Partnership Dynamics	Council Partnerships	Partner volume by council	Counts of project partners or organisation-project pairs by council, with choice of link table and counting method.	Q2, Q4
Partnership Dynamics	Partner Averages	Partner intensity	Average partner counts by council and project type, supporting comparison of collaboration intensity.	Q2, Q4
Partnership Dynamics	Sector Diversity	Partner sectors	Sector/subsector composition of project partners and how this varies by council and funding instrument.	Q2, Q4
Partnership Dynamics	Sector Hierarchy	Sector structure	Hierarchical views of partner sectors and subsectors, useful for identifying dominant partner ecosystems.	Q2, Q4
Partnership Dynamics	Partner Deep-Dive	Detailed partner records	Drill-down tables for selected partner sectors, councils, project types, and organisations.	Q2, Q4
Partnership Dynamics	Partnership Map	Partner geography	Geographic distribution of partner organisations, including place-level summaries and maps.	Q2, Q4
Partnership Dynamics	Interdisciplinarity	Partner-linked search diversity	Diversity metrics based on research-topic or subject classifications, including entropy and Gini-Simpson measures.	Q2, Q4
Organisation Dynamics	Organisation Collaborations	Organisation participation	Role mix, top organisations, co-organisation pairs, and network previews for organisation collaboration patterns.	Q2, Q4
Funding Outcomes	Outcome Timeseries	Outputs over time	Publications, dissemination, policy outputs, collaborations, spinouts, intellectual property, and other outcomes over time.	Q3, Q4
Funding Outcomes	Outcome Comparison	Council-outcome comparison	Council-by-outcome heatmaps and proportional outcome-mix views for comparing output profiles.	Q3, Q4

3 Funding Scale and Organisational Participation

Here we use *High-Level Info* to analyse the scale of applicant-led funding, the organisations participating in it, and how applicant-led funding varies across councils.

3.1 Project-type distribution

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

High-Level Info → *Funding Trends*

Set **Project Type** = All and **Councils** = All Councils to inspect the full project-type distribution across the enhanced database.

The *Funding Trends* view compares the distribution of projects across the operational project-type taxonomy. Just for context, Applicant-led projects are the largest group, with 44,215 projects out of 85,627 (51.6%). Thematic projects represent 11,401 projects (13.3%), training 8,971 (10.5%), fellowship 5,755 (6.7%), follow-up 1,495 (1.7%), institutional 1,190 (1.4%), and infrastructure 676 (0.8%). A further 11,924 projects remain uncertain because the available scheme and call metadata were insufficient for confident assignment.

Set **Project Type** = Applicant-Led and compare applicant-led results across councils. Do the same, but setting **Project Type** = All to obtain the results grouping all types of projects, and compare results across councils. The share of projects classified as applicant-led varies substantially by council. In the dashboard summaries (shown in Figures 2, and 3) EPSRC and BBSRC show high applicant-led shares, while NERC and AHRC have lower shares under this classification. This does not mean that these councils are less active overall; rather, it shows that the balance between applicant-led, targeted/thematic, training, fellowship, infrastructure, and other funding instruments differs across councils.

Figure 2: Funding trends for applicant-led funded projects over years across councils.

Figure 3: Funding trends for all types funded projects over years across councils.

Table 3: Council-level applicant-led shares from the *High-Level Info* → *Funding Trends* view.

Council	Applicant-led projects / all projects	Share
AHRC	2,758 / 8,303	33.2%
BBSRC	9,140 / 15,678	60.8%
EPSRC	15,868 / 24,163	65.7%
ESRC	4,360 / 8,928	48.8%
MRC	6,313 / 12,076	52.3%
NC3Rs	257 / 493	52.1%
NERC	3,267 / 10,453	31.3%
STFC	2,252 / 5,526	40.8%

3.2 Dominant organisations and long-tail participation

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

High-Level Info → *Participation Explorer*

Use the left-hand filters to select **Project Type = Applicant-Led**, **Council = All Councils**, and the preferred organisation identity mode. For institution-level analysis, use the canonical organisation option, so that raw name variants are grouped under a single organisation identity.

The *Participation Explorer* shows that a small number of large research organisations account for a high number of applicant-led projects, while a long tail of organisations participate in relatively few projects. Across funding types, large research-intensive organisations such as Oxford, UCL, Cambridge, Imperial, Edinburgh, and Manchester appear repeatedly among the highest-participation groups.

Table 4: Illustrative top organisations by project type, based on the *High-Level Info* → *Participation Explorer* view.

Project type	Frequently observed top organisations
All projects	Oxford, UCL, Cambridge, Imperial, Edinburgh
Applicant-led	UCL, Oxford, Cambridge, Imperial, Manchester
Thematic	Oxford, Edinburgh, UCL, Imperial, Cambridge
Training	UCL, Manchester, Oxford, Cambridge, Edinburgh
Fellowship	Oxford, UCL, Cambridge, Imperial, Edinburgh
Infrastructure	Edinburgh, Manchester, UCL, EMBL, Cambridge
Follow-up	Leeds, Edinburgh, Oxford, Manchester, UCL
Institutional	Edinburgh, Nottingham, Manchester, Rothamsted Research, Bristol

Figure 4: Participation Explorer view for applicant-led projects, showing the participation distribution, the spread of project counts across organisations, and the top participating organisations.

Figure 4 illustrates the concentration and long-tail structure of applicant-led participation. The top panel shows that a small group of large universities account for a large number of applicant-led projects. The lower panels show that most organisations have very low project counts, while a small number of organisations are clear high-participation outliers. This pattern is important for policy questions about concentration, institutional reach, and whether applicant-led funding supports a broad organisational base or is concentrated around a small set of research-intensive institutions; such questions are commonly formalised through concentration or inequality measures such as the Gini coefficient [1].

The dashboard therefore supports two complementary readings. At the top of the distribution, it identifies recurring institutional actors across funding modes. At the lower end, the long tail indicates broad participation by many smaller or less frequent organisations. The option to switch between raw and canonical organisation identities is important here, because it reduces fragmentation caused by name variants and makes organisation-level participation patterns more interpretable.

3.3 Team Composition

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

High-Level Info → *Team Composition*

Use the left-hand filters to compare **Project Type = Applicant-Led** and **Project Type = Thematic**, with **Council = All Councils**. The same tab can also be rerun for **Training**, **Fellowship**, **Infrastructure**, or **All** to compare team structures across funding instruments.

(a) Applicant-led projects.

(b) Targeted/thematic projects.

Figure 5: *GTR Analyser* Team Composition tab comparing average named team size for applicant-led and targeted/thematic projects by council.

Figure 5 shows that team composition differs between applicant-led and targeted/thematic projects. For applicant-led projects, average named team sizes are highest for STFC and MRC, both above four named researchers per project. ESRC and EPSRC sit in the middle of the distribution, while BBSRC, AHRC, and NERC show smaller average named teams. This suggests that applicant-led projects are not homogeneous: even within the same broad funding type, councils differ in the scale of recorded project teams.

The targeted/thematic view shows larger average named teams across most councils. MRC and ESRC have the highest averages, followed by STFC and EPSRC. AHRC and NERC also show larger average teams than in the applicant-led view, while BBSRC remains the lowest among the councils shown. Overall, targeted/thematic projects appear to involve larger named teams than applicant-led projects, which is consistent with the idea that directed or strategic calls may require larger, more coordinated teams around predefined priorities.

The comparison shows that funding instruments differ not only in project counts, award values, or partner profiles, but also in recorded team structure. These values should be interpreted as counts of *named researchers recorded in GtR*, not as complete staffing counts. Researchers, technicians, research assistants, students, or other staff who were costed into awards but not explicitly listed in the GtR person records may not appear in the dataset. Therefore, actual project teams may be larger than shown here, and the comparison should be read as an analysis of recorded named project teams rather than full workforce size.

3.4 Spatial distribution

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

High-Level Info → *Spatial Explorer*

Set **Organisation Layer** = Canonical (Grouped) and **Aggregate By** = Place (AutoLocation). To compare funding instruments, run the view once with **Project Type** = Applicant-Led and once with **Project Type** = Thematic. Users can inspect all councils together, as shown here, or select individual councils from the left-hand filter panel. The same tab also includes a map representation of the geographic concentration of projects. In addition, users can change the

aggregation mode, for example grouping by organisation name rather than place, to move between institutional and geographic views.

(a) Applicant-led projects.

(b) Thematic projects.

Figure 6: *GTR Analyser* Spatial Explorer view comparing the distribution of applicant-led and thematic projects by place. Bars are stacked by council.

Figure 6 compares the place-level distribution of applicant-led and thematic projects. Both funding types are concentrated in major UK research hubs, especially London, with additional activity across established university cities and regions. This reflects the concentration of UKRI-funded activity around large research-intensive organisations and places.

However, the two funding instruments show different spatial profiles. Applicant-led projects have a broader spread across several major university cities and regions. London remains the largest location, but places such as Edinburgh, East of England, Manchester, Bristol, Glasgow, Birmingham, Leeds, Nottingham, Sheffield, and York also show substantial activity. Thematic projects are also concentrated in London, with notable activity in the South East and several other hubs, suggesting a more spatially concentrated pattern.

The stacked bars also show that the council mix changes across places and funding instruments. In the applicant-led view, EPSRC and BBSRC contribute strongly across many locations, while MRC, ESRC, AHRC, NERC, and STFC add smaller but visible shares in several places. In the thematic view, activity is more uneven: London dominates the distribution, with large contributions from several councils, while the South East is also prominent and other places show lower volumes. The *Spatial Explorer* view therefore separates three effects that would otherwise be conflated: where projects are concentrated, which councils drive that concentration, and whether a funding instrument has a broad or narrow geographic footprint. In this case, applicant-led funding appears more widely distributed across major university cities, whereas thematic funding is more clustered around London and a smaller number of high-volume hubs.

4 Partnership Dynamics

This section uses the *GTR Analyser* views under *Partnership Dynamics* to analyse how different funding instruments vary in their partner intensity, partner-sector composition, and collaboration architecture. The focus remains on applicant-led funding, with comparisons to thematic and other project types where relevant.

4.1 Average number of partners

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

Partnership Dynamics → *Partner Averages*

Use the left-hand filters to compare **Project Type = Applicant-Led** and **Project Type = Thematic**. Users can inspect all councils together, as shown here, or select individual councils from the filter panel. The dashboard can also be rerun with different counting modes, such as partner links, distinct partner organisations, or organisation-project pairs, depending on whether the analysis is focused on relationship volume, partner breadth, or repeated participation.

(a) Applicant-led projects.

(b) Thematic projects.

Figure 7: *GTR Analyser* Partner Averages view comparing the average number of partners per project for applicant-led and thematic projects by council.

Figure 7 shows that partner intensity differs substantially between applicant-led and thematic funding. For applicant-led projects, EPSRC has the highest average number of partners per project, followed by STFC, MRC, ESRC, NERC, AHRC, BBSRC, and NC3Rs.³ This pattern indicates that applicant-led funding is not a single collaboration model: some councils, especially EPSRC, support applicant-led projects with relatively strong partner engagement, while others show more modest average partner counts.

The thematic view shows a much stronger outlier pattern. EPSRC thematic projects have a much higher average number of partners per project than all other councils, while NERC, ESRC, AHRC, MRC, BBSRC, and STFC have lower and more similar values. NC3Rs does not appear in the thematic chart because, under the current filters and project-type classification, there are no NC3Rs thematic projects represented in this view.

³NC3Rs refers to the National Centre for the Replacement, Refinement and Reduction of Animals in Research. It is a specialist 3Rs funder/centre rather than a UKRI research council in the same sense as AHRC, BBSRC, EPSRC, ESRC, MRC, NERC, or STFC, but it appears in the GtR data as an administrator/funder category.

This comparison suggests that funding instruments differ not only in scale and award value, but also in collaboration architecture. Applicant-led funding shows moderate council-level variation in partner intensity, whereas thematic funding is more uneven, with EPSRC thematic projects standing out as especially partner-intensive. This is consistent with the idea that some thematic or challenge-oriented instruments may be designed to coordinate larger partner ecosystems, while applicant-led funding may support a broader range of project structures.

4.2 Partner-sector composition

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

Partnership Dynamics → *Sector Diversity*

and:

Partnership Dynamics → *Sector Hierarchy*

Set **Project Type** = **Applicant-Led** to inspect partner sectors for applicant-led projects, and rerun the same views with **Project Type** = **Thematic** or **All** to compare funding instruments. Users can also filter by council to inspect council-specific partner ecosystems. The *Sector Diversity* tab provides broad sector-level comparisons, while the *Sector Hierarchy* tab allows users to inspect more detailed subsector structures. The interpretation also depends on the selected counting mode: **Distinct orgs** reflects the breadth of the partner network, **Partner links** reflects overall partnering activity, and **Org-project pairs** reflects how often organisations participate across projects.

The sector/subsector enrichment layer enables the dashboard to compare the types of organisations that appear as project partners. This is important because the raw organisation-type fields are often too broad, missing, or inconsistent to support reliable partner analysis.

Figure 8: *GTR Analyser* Sector Diversity view showing the sector composition of partner organisation–project pairs for applicant-led projects, grouped by council.

Figure 8 shows that partner-sector composition varies strongly by council for applicant-led projects. EPSRC has by far the largest number of partner organisation–project pairs, with a particularly strong contribution from *Industry/Commercial* partners and a substantial *HE/Research* component. This suggests that EPSRC applicant-led projects have a distinctive partner ecosystem involving both academic/research organisations and commercial partners.

Other councils show different sector profiles. AHRC has a visible *Culture/Heritage* component, consistent with engagement with museums, galleries, libraries, archives, and other cultural organisations. MRC and NC3Rs show comparatively stronger links with *Healthcare* organisations, while ESRC includes a more mixed profile involving *Public sector*, *Non-profit/Charity*, and *Professional Services* partners. NERC also shows a strong *HE/Research* and *Industry/Commercial* profile, while STFC has a smaller partner volume in this view. Several distinctive patterns are visible in the dashboard views:

- AHRC is distinctive in its links with culture and heritage organisations, including museums, galleries, libraries, and archives.

- BBSRC, EPSRC, NERC, and STFC show strong links with private companies and research organisations.
- MRC and NC3Rs are distinctive in their links with hospitals, NHS trusts, and healthcare organisations.
- ESRC shows substantial engagement with charities, non-profit organisations, public bodies, and local or regional authorities.
- Government departments appear more prominently in thematic funding than in applicant-led funding.

These findings show why sector and subsector inference is valuable. Raw organisation-type labels alone would not provide enough granularity to distinguish museums, local authorities, healthcare organisations, charities, public bodies, and private companies in a consistent way across councils. The *Sector Diversity* and *Sector Hierarchy* tabs therefore make it possible to compare not only how many partners different funding instruments involve, but also what kinds of partners they engage.

4.3 Partner-linked interdisciplinarity

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

Partnership Dynamics → *Interdisciplinarity*

Use **Project Type** = **Applicant-Led**, **Thematic**, or **All** to compare funding instruments. The tab allows users to select the organisation layer, council filters, counting method, link table, and interdisciplinarity basis, for example **ResearchTopicSubject**. It reports complementary diversity metrics including average distinct categories, entropy, and Gini-Simpson diversity.

The *Interdisciplinarity* tab extends the partnership analysis from *how many partners?* and *what types of partners?* to the research-area diversity associated with partnered projects. The average number of distinct categories indicates how many research areas are represented in partnered projects; entropy captures how evenly activity is distributed across categories [2]; and Gini-Simpson diversity captures the probability that two category assignments are different, providing a measure of topic mixing [3]. Together, these measures follow a broader tradition of using diversity indicators to analyse variety, balance, and distribution across categories [4].

4.3.1 All project types

Across all project types, AHRC, ESRC, and NC3Rs show relatively high average distinct-category counts, while MRC and EPSRC show lower values in the dashboard outputs. Entropy and Gini-Simpson values also indicate that AHRC and ESRC have more evenly balanced category distributions and stronger topic mixing than some other councils as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Research-area diversity metrics for all project types across councils.

4.3.2 Applicant-led projects

For applicant-led projects, the same measures are broadly similar in scale to the all-project view, but the council ordering changes (see Figure 10). ESRC shows the highest average distinct-category count, and both ESRC and AHRC show relatively high entropy and Gini-Simpson values. This suggests that applicant-led projects in these councils have broader and more evenly distributed research-area coverage. EPSRC and STFC show lower values in this view. The similarity between the all-project and applicant-led values is expected because applicant-led projects constitute the largest project-type group in the enhanced database.

Figure 10: Research-area diversity metrics for applicant-led projects across councils.

4.3.3 Thematic projects

Thematic projects show stronger changes in the diversity metrics, visible in Figure 11. The average number of distinct categories is higher than in the applicant-led view for several councils, and the ordering of councils changes substantially. In the dashboard outputs, STFC thematic projects show the highest values across the three diversity measures, while BBSRC is lower. This is notable because a simple expectation might be that thematic calls are narrower. Instead, the observed metrics suggest that some thematic instruments may deliberately bring together multiple research areas around a shared challenge or priority.

Figure 11: Research-area diversity metrics for thematic projects across councils.

4.3.4 Weighted and unweighted topic views

The dashboard also compares weighted and unweighted views of research-area rankings. When every project is counted equally, large project ecosystems no longer dominate the same way they do under funding-weighted or link-weighted views. The delta plots in Figures 12, 13, 14 show which classification descriptions become more prominent when the analysis treats projects equally rather than allowing large ecosystems to dominate.

Figure 12: Rank changes between weighted and unweighted classification views for all project types. Positive values indicate classifications that rise when each project is counted equally.

Figure 13: Rank changes between weighted and unweighted classification for applicant-led.

Figure 14: Rank changes between weighted and unweighted classification for thematic projects.

The repeated high-delta classifications across all-project, applicant-led, and thematic views should be treated as a prompt for further validation. Such repeated patterns may reflect robust structural features in the classification data, but they may also indicate that the weighting calculation or filtering logic should be checked in the dashboard and database queries. This diagnostic function is useful because the dashboard is not only a reporting interface; it also helps identify modelling assumptions, data-quality issues, and new questions for follow-up analysis.

5 Outputs and Outcomes

This section uses the *GTR Analyser* views under *Funding Outcomes* to analyse reported outputs and outcomes associated with different project types. The dashboard includes outcome records such as publications, dissemination activities, collaborations, further funding, databases and models, policy outputs, key findings, impact summaries, research materials, technical products, creative products, intellectual property, spinouts, and other outputs.

5.1 Outcome time series and totals

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

Funding Outcomes → *Timeseries*

and:

Funding Outcomes → *Totals*

Use **Project Type = All, Applicant-Led, or Thematic** to compare outcome profiles across funding instruments. Users can inspect all councils together, as shown here, or select individual councils from the filter panel. The *Timeseries* tab shows reported outcomes over time, while the *Totals* tab summarises the aggregate number of reported outcomes by outcome type.

Across all project types and councils, publications dominate the outcome record every year. Dissemination activities are the second-largest outcome type, but remain below publications in most years. This pattern is visible both in the time-series (Figure 15) view and in the total outcome table (Figure 16).

Figure 15: *GTR Analyser* Funding Outcomes → Timeseries view showing reported outcomes over time for all project types and all councils.

Outcome Type	Outcomes	Projects	Outcomes per Project	Share (%)
publication	1455693	58491	24.887	55.95
dissemination	577568	36079	16.008	22.20
collaboration	172129	30145	5.710	6.62
furtherfunding	116414	27223	4.276	4.47
databaseandmodel	67351	14859	4.533	2.59
policy	52329	11696	4.474	2.01
keyfinding	45907	45907	1.000	1.76
creativeproduct	34904	5943	5.873	1.34
impactssummary	31780	31780	1.000	1.22
researchmaterial	20468	9424	2.172	0.79
technicalproduct	16554	6691	2.474	0.64
ip	6198	3152	1.966	0.24
prodint	2307	1280	1.802	0.09
spinout	2222	1712	1.298	0.09

Figure 16: *GTR Analyser* Funding Outcomes → Totals view showing total outcomes by type for all project types and all councils.

5.2 Applicant-led projects

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

Funding Outcomes → *Timeseries*

and:

Funding Outcomes → *Totals*

Set **Project Type = Applicant-Led** and **Councils = All Councils**. The same views can be rerun for selected councils to inspect council-specific outcome patterns.

Applicant-led projects show a similar overall pattern to the all-project view (Figures 17, 18). Publications dominate, followed by dissemination activities and collaborations. Because applicant-led projects form the largest project-type group, they account for a substantial share of the overall publication and dissemination patterns in the enhanced database.

Figure 17: *GTR Analyser* Funding Outcomes → Timeseries view showing reported outcomes over time for applicant-led projects across all councils.

Outcome Type	Outcomes	Projects	Outcomes per Project	Share (%)
publication	865906	35648	24.290	60.12
dissemination	282141	20496	13.766	19.59
collaboration	87838	17528	5.011	6.10
furtherfunding	62252	16024	3.885	4.32
databaseandmodel	37874	8972	4.221	2.63
keyfinding	28070	28070	1.000	1.95
policy	21601	5678	3.804	1.50
impactsummary	18187	18187	1.000	1.26
researchmaterial	11653	5757	2.024	0.81
creativeproduct	10213	2856	3.576	0.71
technicalproduct	9090	3939	2.308	0.63
ip	3316	1764	1.880	0.23
spinout	1181	924	1.278	0.08
prodint	1057	601	1.759	0.07

Figure 18: *GTR Analyser* Funding Outcomes → Totals view showing total outcomes by type for applicant-led projects across all councils.

5.3 Thematic projects

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

Funding Outcomes → Timeseries

and:

Funding Outcomes → Totals

Set Project Type = Thematic and Councils = All Councils. The same filters can be changed to compare thematic projects with applicant-led, training, fellowship, infrastructure, follow-up, institutional, or all projects.

Thematic projects differ from applicant-led projects in several respects (Figure 19 and 20). Publications remain important, but the gap between publications and dissemination activities is smaller than in the all-project and applicant-led views. In some recent years, dissemination activities exceed publications, although recent years should be treated cautiously because projects may not yet have had sufficient time to report outputs. Thematic projects also show a visible peak around 2017 across several outcome types, including collaborations, further funding, and databases/models.

Figure 19: *GTR Analyser* Funding Outcomes → Timeseries view showing reported outcomes over time for thematic projects across all councils.

Outcome Type	Outcomes	Projects	Outcomes per Project	Share (%)
publication	243037	7873	30.870	45.06
dissemination	175337	5876	29.840	32.51
collaboration	35270	4587	7.689	6.54
furtherfunding	23599	4047	5.831	4.38
policy	18170	2765	6.571	3.37
databaseandmodel	15350	2660	5.771	2.85
keyfinding	7096	7096	1.000	1.32
creativeproduct	6859	1323	5.184	1.27
impactsummary	5622	5622	1.000	1.04
researchmaterial	4041	1544	2.617	0.75
technicalproduct	3404	1045	3.257	0.63
ip	864	398	2.171	0.16
prodint	363	223	1.628	0.07
spinout	325	244	1.332	0.06

Figure 20: *GTR Analyser* Funding Outcomes → Totals view showing total outcomes by type for thematic projects across all councils.

5.4 Council-level outcome comparison

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

Funding Outcomes → *Comparison*

Use **Project Type = All, Applicant-Led, or Thematic** to compare outcome profiles across councils and funding instruments. The *Comparison* tab provides council-by-outcome heatmaps and proportional outcome-mix views, making it easier to identify which councils are associated with particular reported outcome types.

The council-level heatmaps show how outcome types vary by council and project type. Publications dominate across the all-project and applicant-led views, with particularly strong publication counts for large-volume councils such as EPSRC. The thematic view is more differentiated: publications remain important, but dissemination activities, collaborations, further funding, policy outputs, and database/model outcomes are more visible relative to publications than in the applicant-led view. This suggests that thematic projects have a more varied outcome profile across councils.

(a) All project types.

(b) Applicant-led.

(c) Thematic.

Figure 21: *GTR Analyser* Funding Outcomes → Comparison view showing council-level heatmaps of major reported outcome types.

Figure 21 highlights the importance of comparing outcome profiles by project type. In the all-project and applicant-led views, publication counts dominate the heatmap, especially for EPSRC and other high-volume councils. In the thematic view, publications are still visible, but dissemination activities become more prominent, particularly for councils such as ESRC. This makes thematic projects appear more heterogeneous across outcome types and councils than applicant-led projects.

5.5 Outputs excluding publications and dissemination

Dashboard location. This analysis can be performed in *GTR Analyser* using:

Funding Outcomes → *Timeseries*

and:

Funding Outcomes → *Comparison*

Use the dashboard option to exclude dominant outcome types such as publications and dissemination activities. This allows users to inspect lower-volume outcome categories that are otherwise difficult to see in the aggregate charts. Because publications and dissemination activities dominate the outcome record, excluding them reveals otherwise hidden variation in collaborations, further funding, databases/models, policy outputs, creative products, intellectual property, spinouts, research materials, and technical products.

Figure 22: *GTR Analyser* Funding Outcomes → Timeseries view showing reported outcomes over time after excluding publications and dissemination activities.

Figure 23: *GTR Analyser* Funding Outcomes → Comparison view showing council-level heatmaps after excluding publications and dissemination activities.

The time-series views (Figure: 22) show that removing publications and dissemination makes lower-volume outcome types easier to compare. The thematic view suggests that the 2017 peak is not only a publication or dissemination effect: collaborations, further funding, and database/model outcomes also increase. Applicant-led projects show a more gradual increase from around 2011 and a levelling-off from approximately 2013 onwards, subject to the caveat that recent records may be incomplete. Figure 23 shows the value of removing the two dominant outcome categories. In the all-project view, collaborations and further funding become the most visible remaining outcome types, with strong contributions from councils such as EPSRC, BBSRC, MRC, ESRC, and NERC. Database/model outcomes, policy outputs, key findings, research materials, and technical products also become easier to distinguish once publications and dissemination no longer dominate the colour scale.

The applicant-led view shows a more concentrated pattern. EPSRC is particularly visible for collaboration, further funding, databases/models, key findings, and technical products, while MRC and BBSRC also contribute strongly to collaboration and further funding. This suggests that, within applicant-led funding, lower-volume outcomes are still partly shaped by large councils and high-volume project portfolios.

The thematic view is more heterogeneous across councils and outcome types. EPSRC remains prominent for collaboration and further funding, MRC shows a strong collaboration profile, ESRC has a visible policy-output component, NERC contributes to database/model and key-finding outcomes, and AHRC shows a distinctive creative-products component. This indicates that lower-volume outcome types reveal council- and project-type-specific patterns that are hidden when publications and dissemination dominate the visual scale.

6 Cross-cutting Interpretation

The case study illustrates four ways in which the enhanced GtR database and *GTR Analyser* dashboard support metascience analysis.

- The dashboard makes it possible to compare funding instruments consistently. The project-type taxonomy allows users to move beyond raw scheme and call names and compare applicant-led, targeted/thematic, training, fellowship, infrastructure, follow-up, and institutional funding across councils, years, organisations, partners, research areas, and outcomes. This is essential because the case study shows that applicant-led funding is the largest project-type category, but its relative importance varies by council.
- The enriched organisation layer changes the types of questions that can be asked. Canonical organisations reduce fragmentation caused by duplicated or variant organisation names, enabling clearer analysis of dominant institutions, long-tail participation, and spatial concentration. The case study shows that a small number of large research-intensive organisations account for many projects, while many organisations participate only occasionally. The ability to switch between raw and canonical organisation identities is therefore important for interpreting institutional reach and concentration.
- The sector and subsector enrichment makes partner analysis more informative. The partnership views show that funding instruments differ not only in the number of partners they involve, but also in the types of partners they engage. For example, applicant-led projects show council-specific partner ecosystems, with strong industry/commercial participation in some councils, culture and heritage partners in AHRC, healthcare-related partners in MRC and NC3Rs, and public-sector or charity engagement in ESRC. These patterns would be difficult to analyse using raw organisation-type fields alone.
- The dashboard supports diagnostic analysis as well as reporting. Several observations require further investigation, including the strong EPSRC outlier in thematic partner

averages, the repeated delta patterns in the weighted and unweighted classification rankings, the thematic outcome peak around 2017, and council-specific differences in lower-volume outcome types once publications and dissemination are excluded. These examples show that the dashboard is not only a presentation layer, but also a tool for identifying data-quality issues, modelling assumptions, and new research questions.

7 Conclusion

This companion case study demonstrates how the *GTR Analyser* dashboard can be used to analyse UKRI funding instruments at multiple levels: projects, councils, organisations, places, partners, sectors, research areas, and outcomes. The results show that applicant-led funding is the largest project-type category and shapes many all-project trends, but it is not homogeneous across councils. Councils differ in their applicant-led shares, average award values, partner intensity, spatial footprint, and outcome profiles.

The comparison with targeted/thematic funding shows that targeted or thematic instruments display distinctive patterns. Thematic projects appear more uneven in partner intensity, with a strong EPSRC outlier; they also show higher or differently distributed interdisciplinarity in some council views, more spatial concentration in major hubs, and more heterogeneous outcome profiles once publications and dissemination are separated from lower-volume outputs. These differences demonstrate why project-type classification, canonical organisation grouping, sector/subsector inference, and dashboard-based filtering are necessary for comparative analysis.

More broadly, the case study illustrates the value of converting raw administrative funding records into an enriched, queryable, and visually explorable metascience infrastructure. The dashboard allows non-technical users to recompute analyses by project type, council, organisation identity, geography, partner type, and outcome category without writing SQL. It also helps identify patterns that require further validation.

Future work will validate the observed thematic peak around 2017, investigate council-level differences in partner and outcome profiles, and compare weighted and unweighted classification views more systematically. We will also extend the dashboard with linked evidence sources such as OpenAlex, and refine the funding taxonomy to distinguish responsive-mode funding within the broader applicant-led category.

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